

FEASIBILITY TRIAL OF AN INTERVENTION TO IMPROVE ATTENDANCE AT DIABETIC RETINOPATHY SCREENING

TOPIC GUIDE (PATIENT)

- Thank participant, introduce researcher & study
- Outline information sheet, consent form, highlight permission to record interview
- Important to stress that they can be honest about their experience; their data will be only shared within the research team and will not be provided to the practice
- **Study explanation:** There is a national screening programme available to you, that your GP registers you for. We are doing a study about that programme and why people decide to go or not

Topic	Prompt/probe
<p>Introduction Tell me a bit about yourself</p>	
<p>Screening Have you ever had your eyes screened for diabetic retinopathy?</p> <p>Had you heard of the national retinal screening programme (Diabetic RetinaScreen)?</p>	<p>When? Where? How often? If yes: why? (e.g. HCP told them, benefits, control, free) If no: why not? (e.g. forget, already checked, no risk, fear, drops, difficult, denial, cost)</p> <p>How did you hear about it?</p>
<p>Receiving the intervention Did your GP/nurse tell you about retinopathy screening? Can you tell me how that went?</p> <p>Did you receive a letter and leaflet from your practice about screening?</p> <p>Had you ever heard about diabetes and eye problems? Have you ever been told by anyone else that people with diabetes needed eye screening?</p> <p>Is that something which would usually happen? (GP/nurse calling you, or reminding in person)</p>	<p>When was that (at practice and/or over phone)? What did they say? Do you remember what they said about screening?</p> <p>What did you do after that? Why did you do that? What did you think/feel about that? (e.g. trust, reassured, knowledge of consequences, efficacy/support to act) Anything stand out; was there something you particularly remembered about what they said? Did it influence what you thought about screening? (e.g. risk/benefits, fear, necessity)</p> <p>[If don't remember] What do you think of that leaflet? What do you think about getting things in the post from your practice?</p>
<p>Intervention influence Do you think the reminders [in person/phone/letter reminders/information leaflet] encouraged you to consent or attend screening?</p>	<p>Which part? If yes/no, why do you think that was? (e.g. competing demands, location)</p> <p>What was it about... ...the GP/nurse reminding in person or by phone? ...receiving a letter?</p>

	<p>...receiving the leaflet? ...that made the difference? Why?</p> <p>If no, did you consent/attend in the end? If not because of the intervention, then why was that?</p>
<p>Recommendations Thinking about the reminders overall [inperson/phone/letter/information leaflet] what did you like/dislike?</p>	<p>What did you think was good about it? (e.g. trusted source, offer of support, risk/benefit information, reassurance) Is there anything which would make it better? Is there anything which you would add to or change?</p> <p>Do you think it would have made a difference if someone else at the practice rang you / told you about screening?</p>
<p>We are conducting a pilot ('test run') to inform a bigger version of this study. How did you find the different parts of how the study was run (prompts)? How you would improve it?</p>	<p>(as applicable) e.g. invitation letter, study explanation by practice/research team, practice poster</p>
<p>To finish Is there anything else you want to mention about your experience?</p>	